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Luminosity at LHCb in Run 3

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Abstract

The physics performance of the LHCb detector in Runs 1 and 2 was optimised by stabilising the instantaneous luminosity during each fill. This was achieved by tuning the distance between the two colliding beams according to the measurement of instantaneous luminosity from hardware-based trigger counters. The upgraded LHCb detector operates at fivefold instantaneous luminosity compared to the previous runs. Consequently, a new approach to the luminosity measurement is adopted. New counters, with particular attention to maximum stability in time, and a new dedicated detector have been introduced for Run 3. Presented here is an overview of the newly implemented methods for luminosity measurement and the first results obtained using data collected during 2022.

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1 Luminosity at LHCb

The centre of mass energy, \sqrt{s} , and the luminosity, \mathcal{L} , are typically amongst the most important quantities characterising a particle collider. Integrated luminosity can be defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} \equiv \int \mathcal{L} dt \equiv \frac{1}{\sigma_c} \int R_c(t) dt, \quad (1)$$

where σ_c and $R_c(t)$ are the cross section of some process, c , and the rate at which it occurs, respectively. Measurements of the absolute luminosity, \mathcal{L}_{int} are crucial inputs to any production cross section measurement. At the LHCb experiment this is calibrated by the complementary van der Meer (vdM) and beam-gas imaging (BGI) analyses in special fills approximately once per year, per beam energy and per beam type.

The integrated luminosity can also be expressed for a single colliding bunch pair as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \frac{\mu_c n}{\sigma_c}, \quad (2)$$

where μ_c is the mean number of occurrences of the process c per bunch crossing and n is the number of bunch crossings. The quantity μ_c is referred to as the relative luminosity, and the process c is known as a luminosity counter. The relative luminosity is used as an input to the absolute calibration analyses, for propagating the absolute calibration results to calculate the recorded ‘physics’ luminosity, and for online monitoring during data taking. The latter purpose is particularly important at LHCb, where a procedure known as luminosity levelling is utilised to optimise detector performance by maintaining a constant luminosity with a precision of $\lesssim 10\%$ – as far as beam intensity decay allows – throughout each fill. To achieve this, the beams collide with an offset at the beginning of each fill and are gradually brought to head-on, keeping μ_c constant. This is illustrated in Figure 1 (left).

Figure 1: Evolution of instantaneous luminosity throughout fill 2651 for ATLAS, CMS and LHCb to illustrate the levelling procedure at LHCb, adapted from [1] (left). Ratio of ‘track’ and ‘vertex’ counters at LHCb in pp collisions at 13 TeV throughout the entire LHC Run 2 (right).

Throughout Runs 1 and 2 the relative luminosity at LHCb was measured with the so-called ‘LogZero’ method [2] by counting the fraction of ‘empty’ events. Empty events are defined as those where a given process is not observed or a given detector threshold is not passed, e.g. < 2 reconstructed VELO tracks, or below a minimum E_T deposit in the calorimeter. The relationship between μ_c and the fraction of empty events can be derived as

$$-\log \left(\frac{n_{\text{empty}}}{n_{\text{total}}} \right) = -\log \left(\frac{\mu_c^0 \exp(-\mu_c)}{0!} \right) = \mu_c, \quad (3)$$

by assuming the number of interactions is distributed according to Poisson statistics. The LogZero method relies on each counter having a reasonable fraction of empty events. For Run 3

the average number of visible interactions will increase by a factor of ~ 5 , which may necessitate a different approach; studies are ongoing in this respect. A suitable luminosity counter has the following properties: a cross section that is independent of the luminosity; robustness to radiation damage to the detector and other factors which change over time; independence from other external factors such as the LHC filling scheme. Counters relying on higher-level quantities such as reconstructed tracks and vertices generally performed better than those relying on lower-level quantities such as detector occupancy – particularly in higher occupancy regions of the detector – in Runs 1 and 2 at LHCb. Studies are ongoing to provide luminosity counters from every sub-detector for Run 3, which will allow robust cross-checks of the linearity of each individual counter. The ratio of the two ‘best’ counters for pp collisions at 13 TeV throughout the entirety of Run 2 is shown in Figure 1 (right), demonstrating excellent stability. Since LHCb will operate at a much higher luminosity in Run 3, particularly with regards to the luminosity calibration fills, an emittance scan procedure [3] has been developed to verify linearity by monitoring counter cross sections at the beginning of every fill.

2 The LHCb detector

The LHCb detector is a single arm spectrometer covering the region $2 < \eta < 5$, optimised for studies of b - and c -hadron decays. The experiment has recently undergone a major upgrade programme to prepare for Run 3 of the LHC [4]. PLUME (Probe for LUminosity MEasurements), a new luminometer – detailed in Section 2.1 – has been installed and commissioned. The SMOG (System for Measuring the Overlap with Gas) gas injection system has been upgraded to a gas cell system, SMOG2, described in Section 2.2.

Figure 2: Front view (left) and side view (right) of the layout of the PLUME luminometer PMT arrangement [5].

2.1 PLUME

For Run 3, a dedicated luminosity monitoring sub-detector, PLUME [5], has been successfully installed and commissioned. The primary function of PLUME is to provide online relative luminosity measurements to the LHC with an accuracy of $\sim 10\%$ and an integration time of ~ 3 s. This function was fulfilled by the hardware trigger level using information from the calorimeters in Runs 1 and 2. PLUME, shown in Figure 2 is constructed as a hodoscope of 24 Hamamatsu R760 photomultiplier tubes (PMT) pairs. Each PMT has a 10 mm diameter photocathode and a 1.2 mm thick quartz entrance window; an additional optically connected 5 mm thick quartz tablet increases production of Cherenkov photons. Two PMT pairs are dedicated to fine timing measurements with a resolution of ~ 100 ps. This will allow for monitoring clock shifts between the LHC and LHCb and for probing the bunch structures of one of the LHC beams. PLUME measurements will also be used for absolute calibrations with

vdM and BGI. The design is optimised for an occupancy of $\mathcal{O}(1\%)$ to provide a reliable input to the LogZero method.

Figure 3: Longitudinal primary vertex position distribution with SMOG2 Ar injection, reproduced from [6] (left). Crossing angle measurement using beam-gas vertices with SMOG2 injection (right).

2.2 SMOG2 and ghost charge measurements

In Runs 1 and 2, SMOG allowed luminosity measurements by directly reconstructing the individual beam profiles from beam-gas interactions [7]. The ability to collect both colliding-beam and fixed-target physics data simultaneously was demonstrated. SMOG’s success led to the development of the SMOG2 cell, which has now been installed for Run 3. SMOG2 is a gas storage cell upstream of the VELO which opens and closes with the VELO motion system [8]. The gas cell, contrasted with gas injection throughout the entire VELO vessel using SMOG, allows gas areal densities of at least an order of magnitude higher than SMOG for the same gas flow rate. SMOG2 can inject H_2 , D_2 , or any noble gas; a successful commissioning programme has taken place involving injections with H_2 , He and Ar to date. Figure 3 (left) shows the longitudinal position of a sample of primary vertices reconstructed with SMOG2 active, demonstrating LHCb operating simultaneously with two interaction regions.

Figure 4: Comparison of LHCb and LHC ghost charge measurements for fill 8379 (2022 LHCb and ALICE vdM) for beam 1 (left) and beam 2 (right), reproduced from [9].

Beam-gas interactions also allow relative measurements of the charge distribution around the LHC ring. Measurements of the bunch populations are a crucial ingredient to absolute luminosity calibration measurements. At the LHC, these are provided by per-bunch measurements from the Fast Beam Current Transformers (FBCTs) normalised to the – more precise – Direct Current Current Transformers (DCCTs). Corrections must be applied for erroneous contributions known as ‘ghost’ (outside the filled bunch slots) and ‘satellite’ (inside filled bunch slots, outside central

radio-frequency bucket) charges. The ghost charge fraction can be measured from the ratio of beam-gas vertices produced in filled bunch crossings to that in empty bunch crossings. Figure 4 shows a comparison between measurements obtained during the 2022 LHC vdM programme with Ar injection in SMOG2 and independent LHC measurements from the longitudinal density monitors.

3 Absolute calibration measurements

At hadron collider experiments there are no experimentally simple and theoretically precise cross sections with which to calibrate the absolute luminosity, unlike e.g. Bhabha scattering at e^+e^- machines. The most well known procedure for calibrating the luminosity is the aforementioned vdM method. This involves scanning the two beams across one another and effectively integrating out the beam profiles [10]. This results in the relation

$$\sigma_c = \int \frac{\mu_c(\Delta x, \Delta y)}{N_1 N_2} d\Delta x d\Delta y, \quad (4)$$

where Δx , Δy are the difference between the mean position of the beam profile densities in each of the transverse directions, and N_1 and N_2 are the bunch populations for each beam. This integral is typically factorised under the assumption $\rho(x, y) = \rho(x)\rho(y)$, where ρ represents some normalised density distribution for each beam. Non-factorisation effects were found to be one of the dominant systematic uncertainties in vdM scans during Run 1 of the LHC [2]; a new 2D scan approach was pioneered at LHCb during Run 2 [11, 12]. This is expected to be more widely adopted by the other experiments during Run 3. The first absolute luminosity calibrations with the LHCb detector at 13.6 TeV in a dedicated LHC fill were performed at the end of 2022. Figure 5 shows the beam movements and relative PLUME values during one vdM scan, along with a fit to the relative luminosity to extract the cross section. Studies are ongoing to verify the linearity of counters for PLUME and other sub-detectors.

Figure 5: Evolution of beam positions, bunch intensities and PLUME relative luminosity values during the November 2022 LHCb vdM scans (left). 2D fit to the bunch current normalised PLUME relative luminosity values to extract σ_{PLUME} (right).

LHCb also has a unique capability to calibrate the luminosity by directly measuring the individual beam parameters using reconstructed beam-gas vertices [2]. The absolute luminosity for a single colliding bunch pair can be expressed in terms of the overlap integral of the bunch densities,

$$\int \rho_1(\vec{x}, t) \rho_2(\vec{x}, t) d\vec{x} dt = \frac{e^{-\Delta x^2/2\Sigma_x^2} e^{-\Delta y^2/2\Sigma_y^2}}{4\pi c \Sigma_x \Sigma_y} = \frac{\mathcal{L}}{2cf N_1 N_2}. \quad (5)$$

The first equality assumes the bunch profiles follow a Gaussian distribution; Δx and Δy are the offsets introduced in Equation 4, Σ_x and Σ_y are parameters related to the transverse bunch widths (and potentially the bunch lengths in the presence of a crossing angle) and f is the

LHC revolution frequency. Beam-gas imaging made use of the SMOG system in Runs 1 and 2 to increase the rate of beam-gas vertices. The introduction of the SMOG2 cell leads to a new paradigm where the number of visible beam-gas interactions for one of the beams can approach a similar order of magnitude to the number of visible beam-beam interactions. Figure 3 (right) shows a measurement of the beam crossing angles from beam-gas collisions with SMOG2 injection; the position of the cell is visible as a densely populated area around $z \sim -400$ mm.

4 Conclusions

The LHCb collaboration has almost entirely rebuilt its detector for Run 3 of the LHC. To provide online luminosity monitoring to the LHC for luminosity levelling, a dedicated luminometer – PLUME – has been installed and successfully commissioned. A comprehensive suite of studies are ongoing to identify the best counters in other sub-detectors. The SMOG gas injection system has been replaced with the new SMOG2 cell, which provides new opportunities for fixed target physics and at least an order of magnitude larger beam-gas interaction rate for one of the LHC beams than SMOG. The first luminosity measurements of Run 3 have been performed, namely an absolute calibration of PLUME counters at 13.6 TeV and measurements of the ghost charge fractions.

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